

Novel Coordination Compounds of Mercury(II) with Phenothiazine Drugs

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The method of synthesis and properties of some novel complexes of Hg^{II} with phenothiazine drugs are described. Complexes are of the type HgCl₂.LH, where LH = protonated phenothiazine drugs.

CHEMISTRY of phenothiazine drugs has been growing in recent years into a research field having special interests both in regard to preparative and biological activities. Phenothiazines are excellent electron donors. Metal complexes of phenothiazines exhibit good biological properties^{1,2}. Coordination compounds of phenothiazines with copper(II)³, palladium(II)⁴, platinum(II)⁵, rhodium(III) and ruthenium(III)⁶ are isolated and well characterised. A few genuine coordination compounds of mercury(II) with phenothiazine drugs have been isolated, characterised and herein reported. During the coordination reaction, an unusual change in ligand geometry is observed, which facilitates the reaction between the metal ion and the drugs. The drugs used are shown in Table 1.

zine (CZ) and promazine (PMZ), were from Bayer, Germany. Mercuric chloride (A.R., B.D.H.), was dissolved in double-distilled water with 4-5 drops of concentrated HCl. ¹H nmr spectra of both ligands and the complexes were recorded on a Varian 100 MHz FT nmr spectrometer using deuterated DMSO as the solvent and TMS as internal standard.

Preparation of complexes: An ethanolic solution of ligands was added in 1:1 stoichiometry to an aqueous solution of mercuric chloride followed by the addition of 50 ml of a mixture of acetone and benzene solution. The solution was then refluxed at 70-80° for 5 h on a heating mantel. The product was filtered, washed with ethanol and finally with acetone and vacuum-dried.

The complexes were analysed for mercury content by sulphide method and chloride gravimetrically. The analysis for C, H, N and S were obtained from Micro-Analytical Laboratory, Lucknow.

TABLE 1—LIGANDS USED

Ligand	X	Y
Diethazine (DZ)	OH ₂ CH ₂ NEt ₂	H
Promethazine (PZ)	OH ₂ CHCH ₂ NMe ₂	H
Fluephenazine (FZ)	CH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₂ N(CH ₂) ₂ OH	CF ₃
Mepazine (MZ)	CH ₂ -	H
Chlorpromazine (OZ)	OH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₂ NMe ₂	Cl
Promazine (PMZ)	OH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₂ NMe ₂	H

Experimental

All the phenothiazines were used in their hydrochloride form. Diethazine (DZ), fluephenazine (FZ) and mepazine (MZ) were obtained from May and Baker, India, while, promethazine (PZ), chlorpromazine (CZ) and promazine (PMZ), were from Bayer, Germany.

Results and Discussion

The results of the chemical analysis given in Table 2 indicate the formation of 1:1 complexes of the type HgCl₂.LH, where LH is protonated phenothiazine drugs. These complexes are pale coloured, soluble in DMF, DMSO and CH₃CN, and

TABLE 2—ANALYTICAL RESULTS OF Hg^{II}-PHENOTHIAZINE COMPLEXES

Complex	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)					
	Hg	O	H	N	S	Cl
Hg-DZ	31.22 (31.20)	39.84 (39.62)	3.81 (3.76)	4.48 (4.36)	4.87 (4.99)	22.02 (22.06)
Hg-PZ	33.87 (33.86)	34.54 (34.45)	3.59 (3.57)	4.86 (4.73)	5.33 (5.41)	17.98 (17.95)
Hg-FZ	26.71 (26.89)	35.50 (35.44)	3.78 (3.65)	5.80 (5.64)	4.80 (4.82)	14.22 (14.26)
Hg-MZ	32.57 (32.45)	36.98 (36.89)	3.71 (3.72)	4.48 (4.53)	5.32 (5.19)	17.20 (17.20)
Hg-OZ	32.03 (31.99)	33.45 (32.56)	3.28 (3.21)	4.62 (4.47)	5.15 (5.11)	22.58 (22.62)
Hg-PMZ	34.05 (33.86)	34.76 (34.45)	3.62 (3.57)	4.89 (4.73)	5.47 (5.41)	17.82 (17.95)

are insoluble in C_6H_6 and H_2O . Molar conductance values in DMF ($0.4-1.8 \mu S$) indicate that the complexes are non-electrolytes. Magnetic moment values suggest that the complexes are diamagnetic. On heating the complexes in various solvents, the colour changes from yellow to reddish pink which is most likely due to a dimerization process. Melting points of the complexes could not be recorded due to charring of the complexes on heating above 160° .

Study of the ir spectra of the complexes has shown a considerable back-shift in the C-S bands of the free ligands ($720 s, 690 sh \text{ cm}^{-1}$). This clearly shows the involvement of sulphur atom in the coordination reaction. Further, strong band in the region 300 cm^{-1} is assigned to Hg-S bond. Strong bands in the region $320-340 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the far-ir spectra of the complexes reflect Hg-Cl bond. The possibility of polymeric structure through halogen bridges is ruled out as there were no bands below 300 cm^{-1} in the far-ir spectra of the complexes. Since, all the ligands (DZ, PZ, FZ, MZ, CZ and PMZ) are used in their hydrochloride forms, the drugs remain protonated at the oxocyclic nitrogen with $HgCl_2^+$ being its counterpart. An interaction is observed between the quaternary nitrogen atom at the side chain and the chlorine atom of the $HgCl_2$ unit. This can be seen from the ir spectra of DZ, PZ, FZ, MZ, CZ and PMZ and their Hg^{II} -complexes. In ligands $N^+-H \cdots Cl$ interaction is observed as a strong band at $2300-2640 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. On reaction with Hg^{II} this band moved to $2640-3150 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ with reduced intensity indicating a slight weakening in the hydrogen bonding. Hence, phenothiazines form 1 : 1 complexes with Hg^{II} by donating electron from sulphur to the Hg^{II} ion, and the protonated nitrogen atom forms a hydrogen bonding to $HgCl_2^+$ unit formed during the course of the reaction.

No bands could be seen in the visible spectra of the complexes. However, an $n-\pi^*$ band observed for free ligands in the region $300-326 \text{ nm}$ has been dislocated to the region $340-365 \text{ nm}$. This shift can be taken as an indirect evidence for the complex formation through heterocyclic sulphur atom.

The proton nmr spectra of free ligands show a multiplet at $\delta 7.32-7.43$ due to aromatic protons. This multiplet was unchanged on reaction with the metal chloride. The resonance signals in the region $\delta 2.0-4.0$ found in many of the spectra are not well resolved because of their proximity. The 1H nmr spectrum of DZ shows two triplets of equal intensity at $\delta 2.02$ and single methylene quartet at 3.43 . These are attributed to an accidental overlap of $-N(C_2H_5)_3$ with that of the nitrogen nucleus resonance. There is a considerable back-shift in these two bands on coordination. In PZ and its

complex, the methyl protons of $-C-CH_3$ are highly shielded ones and appear as doublet at $\delta 1.14$ since it is split by CH protons. The two $N-CH_2$ absorbs

at $\delta 2.61$. The resonance signal of CH proton of the side chain is split by both CH_2 protons and

$-C-CH_3$ protons and hence, a double quartet pattern was noticed in the spectrum. The signal due to $>N-CH_2$ was found at $\delta 3.13$ in PZ. The signals of $>N-CH_2$ and $N-CH_2$ were dislocated considerably in the spectrum of complex. In FZ and its complex, the methylene protons of the piperazine ring and the side chain absorbed at approximately the same field which resulted as a broad multiplet structure appear like a triplet corresponding to 14 protons (8 from piperazine ring and 6 from side chain). The methylene protons at the $N-(CH_2)_2OH$ gave a band at $\delta 3.87$. This band has shown a remarkable shift in its position on coordination. The highly shielded methyl protons in MZ appeared at $\delta 2.24$ which has been shifted by about $\delta 0.89$ in the spectrum of its Hg^{II} complex. CZ and PMZ exhibit $N-CH_2$ signals around $\delta 2.72$ as singlet. The methylene protons are found at $\delta 3.87$. The singlet corresponding to $N-CH_2$ protons shifted by about $\delta 1.4$ on complexation is attributed to an intra-molecular hydrogen bonding of the chloride of $HgCl_2$ unit with oxocyclic nitrogen atom, and so in the case of other ligands.

Further, the lines in the 1H nmr spectra of the complexes are shifted with respect to their positions in free ligands come due to two types of effects. The first effect is the change in shielding of the protons due to coordination of the ligand ring. The second effect is due to the proximity of anisotropic groups ('through space'-shift). The net result of these two contributions is the shift that was noticed in the spectra.

From the single crystal X-ray studies, it is noted that on coordination, the ligand molecule is both tilted and twisted with respect to $HgCl_2$ unit. It is also known that phenothiazine ring system is not planar⁷ but possesses a two-fold⁸ character. This helps the side chain containing the nitrogen atom to bend back in a scorpion style to facilitate the participation of the quaternary nitrogen in forming an intra-molecular hydrogen bonding to the chloride atom of $HgCl_2$ unit. The proton on the quaternary

Fig. 1. Molecular structure of $Hg(PZ.H)Cl_2$ complex (H-atoms are omitted for clarity).

nitrogen is projected towards the HgCl_3 unit. The probable molecular structure for one of the complexes with PZ is shown in Fig. 1 in which the central Hg^{II} ion assumes a tetrahedral environment around it. The $\text{H} \cdots \text{Cl}_b$ distance (H from oxocyclic nitrogen and Cl_b from HgCl_3 unit) was found to be 2.28 Å. The intra-molecular hydrogen bond distance $\text{N}_{17} \cdots \text{Cl}_b$ was calculated to be 3.11 Å.

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